

Mental Health, Job Satisfaction and Role Stress of College Teachers.

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Abstract:

The present study is an attempt to determine the relationship among Mental Health, Job Satisfaction and Role stress of college teachers. The sample size of 40 college teachers from the Baramati city was selected. They responded to the tools of Employee Mental Health Inventory (2001), Job Satisfaction Scale (1999) and Roll Stress Scale (1997). The data were collected on the basis of above cited variables. The data were analyzed by using the Pearson's Product Moment Correlation. The obtained findings show that individuals' scoring higher on mental health has showing high on job satisfaction ($r = 0.60$), while low on role stress ($r = -0.51$). It was found that there was negative correlation ($r = -0.37$) between Job Satisfaction and roll stress among college teachers. Findings of the study revealed that the significance of job satisfaction and role stress in maintaining healthy mental health of college teachers.

Keyword: Employee Mental Health, Job Satisfaction, Roll Stress, College Teachers.

Introduction

Teachers are the most powerful agents who influence the behavior of the students and therefore teachers should possess emotional stability as well as healthy attitude towards life. Health of the teacher, both physical and mental, adds to the efficiency of his work. Job satisfaction and work stress are associated very closely in the working environments and that's why certain behaviors appear at work such as organizational behavior employee commitment. Job satisfaction and job performance is directly related to one another. Thus it can be inferred that the happy worker is productive worker. Job satisfaction of teachers is essential for the effective teaching learning process in schools and colleges. We can say that effective teaching is the results of job satisfaction. The teacher who is dissatisfied with his/her work will be unable to motive his/her pupils to attain learning. Present study investigated the phenomenon related to mental health, job satisfaction and role stress among college teachers from an academic point of view which helped them to manage and reduce role stress and to improve the level of mental health and satisfaction on their job. educational workforce especially teachers are enjoying mental health and satisfaction with their jobs, the more they are encouraged to work harder and their capability and the efficiency of the total educational system will rise and will affect the performances of the society in general. Therefore, knowing about the level of mental health job satisfaction and role stress of college teachers in a society matters very much, and in turn can have an important role in the planning of teaching methods and the rise in the efficiency of educational system.

Employee Mental Health:

Health, an indispensable quality in human beings, has been reported as soil from which the finest flower grows. Sound health makes sound mind, adds

to the happiness of a person, and leads to a meaningful and active life. "The preamble of the World Health Organization's charter defined health as a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being, not merely the absence of disease or infirmity. Mental health has been mentioned as the ability of a person to balance one's desires and aspirations, to life stresses and to make psycho-social adjustment. Bhatia (1982) considered mental health as the ability to balance feelings, desires, ambitions and ideals in one's daily living. Anand (1989) has defined mental health as the behavioral characteristics of personality. Dr. Jagdish (2001) defined as the state of mental pleasure and lacking of psycho-physiological complaints. Mental health is about how a person thinks feels and acts when faced with life's situations. Mental health is how people look at themselves, their lives, and the other people in their lives, evaluate their challenges and problems, and explore choices. This includes handling stress, relating to their people, and making decisions. Mental health is far more than the absence of mental illness. Happiness, peace of mind, satisfaction in achievement and enjoyment of life are all aspects of mental health. A person who has good mental health adjusts well with himself and his environment. This is the positive aspect of mental health which is analyzed in the present study.

Job Satisfaction:

Job satisfaction is on attitude that employees have about their work and based on numerous factors, both intrinsic and extrinsic to the individuals. Job satisfaction is important from the retaining the appropriate employees within the organization: it is about fitting the right person to the right job in the right culture and keeping them satisfied. Cranny, Smith, and Stone (1992) wrote that job satisfaction played a central role in the study of people's behavior at work. In academia, individuals such as college teachers possessing a greater sense of job

satisfaction are likely to have a better quality of life, greater physical and mental health, more job stability, and exhibit greater cooperativeness with supervisors. According to Locke (1976) job satisfaction can be viewed as a pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job experience. Robins (1998) defines job satisfaction as it is based on the difference between the amount of rewards workers receive and the amount they believe they should receive. Job satisfaction is a frequently studied subject in work and organizational literature. Job satisfaction is also important in everyday life. Organizations have significant effects on the people who work for them and some of those effects are reflected in how people feel about their work. A person with a high level of job satisfaction holds positive feelings about the job, while a person who is dissatisfied holds negative feelings about the job. According to Shan (1998) teacher job satisfaction is a predictor of teacher retention determinant of teacher commitment and in turn a contributor to school effectiveness. It is expected that a well satisfied teacher would contribute more as compared to a dissatisfied teacher as far as the question of commitments and responsibility pertaining teaching and school environment is concerned.

Roll Stress:

Role is the position one occupies in a social system, and is defined by the functions one performs in response to the expectations of the significant members of a social system, and one's own expectations from that position. The concept of role is vital for the integration of the individual with an organization. The organization has its own structure and goals. Similarly, the individual has his personality and needs. All these aspects interact with each other and to some extent get integrated into a role. Role is also a central concept in work motivation as it is only through this that the individual and organization interact with each other. An organization can be defined as a system of roles. However, a role itself is a system. From the individual's point of view, there are two role systems: the system of various roles that the individual carries and performs, and the system of various roles of which the role is a part. The first is role space and second is a role set. Each individual occupies and plays several roles. A person can be a daughter, a mother, a salesperson, a member of a club, a member of a voluntary organization and so on. All these roles constitute the role space of that person. Stress is an inevitable consequence of socioeconomic complexity and, to some extent, its stimulant as well.

Mental Health and Job Satisfaction:

Khudaniya, K. S. and Dr. Kaji, S. M. (2014) found that the job satisfaction and mental health were

positively correlated, where as mental health and role stress were negatively correlated. It was also found there was negative correlation between role stress and job satisfaction in the case of employees from government and non-government sectors. Devi, D., Dr. Dharamveer and Soni, S. (2013) studied the essential of job satisfaction in effective teaching and they found that there is a positive correlation between job-satisfaction and mental health among teacher educators working in secondary teacher training institutions. Job-satisfaction is dependent upon the mental health of an individual. A mentally healthy person found the more satisfied than the other persons. The study reveals that there is positive relationship between job-satisfaction and mental health.

Mental Health and Roll Stress:

Anand (1986) reported a study on mental health of school teachers using a mental health scale and observed that fifty nine percent of teachers were mentally healthy. This study also reported that the state of working bears no relation to mental health while social values were positively related to mental health of teachers and religious values were negatively correlated.

Job Satisfaction and Roll Stress:

Parsa et.al., (2013) examined the relationship between job stress and job satisfaction and responsiveness among 259 teachers in high schools of Urmia city. Parametric and non parametric test was used for the analysis. The result revealed that there was a significant and positive relationship between responsiveness and job satisfaction and significant and positive relationship between job satisfaction and job stress.

Bhatti et.al. (2011) investigated the relationship between job stress and job satisfaction among 400 university teachers in Pakistan. Management role, relationship with others, workload pressure, homework interface, role ambiguity and performance pressure was examined as determinants of job stress and the result revealed that there was a significant relationship between four of the constructs tested and there is significant negative relationship between job stress and job satisfaction. Result revealed that job stress had negative impact on their health.

A study conducted by Le Rouge, et al (2006) concluded that role stress was positively related to both job satisfaction and organizational commitment and that self-esteem significantly moderated the relationship between role stress fit and job satisfaction.

Objectives:

1. To study the mental health of the college teachers.
2. To Study the job satisfaction of the college teachers.

3. To study the role stress of the college teachers.
4. To find of the relationship among mental health, job satisfaction and role stress of the college teachers.

Hypotheses:

1. There will be positive relationship between mental health and job satisfaction among college teachers.
2. Job satisfaction and roll stress will be inversely correlated.
3. There will be negative relationship between mental health and roll stress.

Methodology:

Sample:

The sample was selected through purposive sampling method. 40 college teachers were selected from various colleges in Baramati city with age range of to years. Clear and loud instructions were given.

Research Design:

Co relational research design is used for the present study.

Data Collection:

The investigators collected the data by taking the prior permission from the college authorities. The topic of the research was introduced to the college teachers to enhance their understanding and for eliciting the co-operation. The tests were presented to the respondent and they were assured that whatever responses they will give would be kept confidential and would be used only for the research purposes. Thus, they were requested to give only honest and true responses. The standardized instructions for the tests were given each time. Data collection was done in small convenient groups on the required sample from five high schools.

Tools used for Data collection:

Three standardized psychological tests were used with addition of personal data sheet for collecting the data.

Employee Mental Health Inventory (EMHI): It was developed by Dr. Jagdish (2001). The EMHI consists of 24 statements which are to be answered in terms of either 'yes' or 'no'. Spilt-half reliability of the test was 0.89. It had been found that EMHI possess content validity as measured with the help of views expressed by experts and judges. Construct validity determined by computing the coefficient of correlation between the scores on EMHI and Mental Health Scale (Buck, 1972), Personal Adjustment (Pestonjee, 1973). The validity coefficient was found to be 0.74 and 0.57.

Job Satisfaction Scale (JSS): The scale developed by Dr. Singh and Dr. Sharma (1999) measures the job satisfaction of respondents through 30 items. Each item is to be answered with the help of 5 point scale ranging from 4 to 0. The test-retest reliability was found to be 0.97. The scale compares favorably

with Muthayya's job satisfaction questionnaire giving a validity coefficient of 0.74.

General Roll Stress Scale: It was constructed by Udai Pareek (1997). Its gives general index of an individual's role stress. It contains 12 items and a respondent rates each item on a 5-point scale (0 to 4). The reliability was found to be 0.79 and validity of the scale was found satisfactory.

Result and Discussion:

Table 1.1 showing descriptive statistics for all variables

Variables	N	Mean	Median	S.D.
Mental Health	30	21.06	22	2.82
Job Satisfaction	30	80.06	79	6.90
Role Stress	30	16.33	16.50	4.28

Table shows the mean, median and Standard deviation on mental health, job satisfaction and role stress. The Mean for mental health is 21.06 and for job satisfaction it is 80.06. The mean for role stress is 28.66 Table 1.2 Correlation between all variables

Variabl es	Mental Health	Job Satisfaction	Role Stress
Mental Health	1		
Job Satisfa ction	0.60**	1	
Role Stress	-0.51**	-0.37*	1

** p< 0.01

* p< 0.05

Table shows the correlation between mental health, job satisfaction and role stress of college teachers. It is seen that there is positive and significant correlation ($r = 0.60, p < 0.01$) between mental health and job satisfaction of college teachers, while mental health is significantly negatively correlated to role stress ($r = -0.51, p < 0.01$) of college teachers. There is negative correlation found between job satisfaction and role stress ($-0.37, p < 0.05$) of college teachers. It means that college teachers those high on job satisfaction shows low score on role stress.

This result shows that college teachers who are good on mental health have shown high level of job satisfaction Earlier studies by Khudaniya, K. S. and Dr. Kaji, S. M. (2014) reported that the job satisfaction and mental health were positively correlated, where as mental health and role stress were negatively correlated. It was also found there was negative correlation between role stress and job satisfaction in the case of employees from government and non-government sectors. Devi, D., Dr. Dharamveer and Soni, S. (2013) found that there is a positive correlation between job-satisfaction and mental health among teacher educators working in secondary teacher training institutions It is conclude that the college teachers who are good on mental health are perceived low role stress. This finding

supported by It is found that college teachers those high on job satisfaction are perceived low level of role stress. Some earlier studies (Bhatti et.al. 2011 and LeRouge, et al 2006) also reported that there is significant negative relationship between job stress and job satisfaction.

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